

The GOGREEN Survey

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This August saw the first public release of advanced data products from the Gemini Observations of Galaxies in Rich Early ENvironments (GOGREEN) survey [1]. The data release was announced during a five-day [workshop](#), sponsored by the [Waterloo Centre for Astrophysics](#). The first days of this workshop were open to the public, and nearly 100 people from around the world attended to hear a description of the survey, the released data products, and the recent and upcoming science results.

GOGREEN is a spectroscopic and imaging survey of 21 overdense galaxy systems in the redshift range $1 < z < 1.5$. The overdensities span a wide range of mass, from groups of only a few galaxies up to the most massive clusters at those early epochs. The spectroscopic program was approved in the first round of Gemini Large and Long Programs in 2014, with an unprecedented allocation of 438 hours on Gemini North and South. Originally planned as a three-year survey, the observations ultimately ran over ten semesters and were completed in mid-2019. Thanks to strong support from Gemini, including program extensions and Director's

Figure 1. These figures show all GOGREEN and GCLASS spectra with robust redshifts in the interval $0.8 < z < 1.5$. The spectra are arranged in order of increasing redshift, from bottom to top as shown on the y-axis. The left panel shows the spectra in observed wavelength, while on the right they are in rest-frame coordinates. The [OII] emission line, 4000 Å break and several absorption lines (indicated at the top of the right panel) are clearly visible. (From [4], with permission)

Discretionary time, the project executed nearly 100 percent of the originally allocated time. In addition to the spectroscopy, deep multiwavelength imaging over the full optical/near-infrared spectrum was obtained from over 100 hours of integration on 4m- and 8m-class facilities around the world. The imaging approaches the depth of the UltraVISTA survey [2] and covers a field of view generally much larger than our GMOS spectroscopy. HST/WFC3 imaging in F160W was also obtained on all clusters; this enables the measurement of structural parameters for most of the spectroscopic sample.

GOGREEN complements the earlier GCLASS cluster survey [3], extending it to higher redshift. The data products from these two surveys were homogenized and combined for the release. The final spectroscopic catalogue consists of 2771 unique

objects, of which 2257 have good redshifts. An overview of the spectroscopic sample in the redshift range $0.8 < z < 1.5$ is shown in Figure 1.

Science goals and survey design

Because of the high spatial density of galaxies at essentially all the same distance from the observer, galaxy clusters provide an efficient way to observe large samples of galaxies, and to uncover fundamental relationships between them. Such observations become very challenging from the ground for clusters at $z > 0.8$, where many of the spectral features we require are shifted to wavelengths where atmospheric absorption and emission, and declining detector sensitivity, become limiting factors.

The upgraded GMOS instrument on Gemini has several unique capabilities that make it ideally suited to observations of distant clusters. The nod-and-shuffle mode enables

excellent sky subtraction at red wavelengths and a high surface density of slits. With a field of view that contains the full virialized cluster volume, it is possible to obtain an unbiased census of the cluster population, including redshifts for hundreds of faint, quiescent galaxies.

In addition to its legacy value, GOGREEN was optimized to address three main topics:

1. *Environmental quenching and growth of the stellar mass function.* Despite a solid theoretical foundation for the gravitational growth of dark matter structure, galaxy formation models struggle to explain: a) the rate of decline in the global star formation rate; b) the mass dependence of this decline; and c) the star formation histories (SFHs) of satellite galaxies. These problems may be related, as they are all sensitive to assumptions about how gas accretion, ejection and heating processes depend on epoch, environment and halo mass [5].
2. *The hierarchical assembly of baryons.* Measurement of the stellar fraction, gas fraction, and star formation rate in haloes of a given mass provides a close link between galaxies and the fundamental prediction of hierarchical assembly from Λ CDM [6]. Precision measurements of this type are critical for calibrating and constraining models, and are an essential complement to abundance-matching and halo occupation model approaches (e.g., [7]).
3. *Cluster Dynamics and Masses.* The distribution and kinematics of cluster galaxies provide crucial information on the total halo mass, independently of X-ray emission and gravitational lensing, especially at high redshift where these other

Figure 2. *Left:* The SMF of quiescent galaxies in the cluster environment ($R < 1$ Mpc), compared to the field. The field is normalized so that it integrates to the same number of quiescent galaxies. *Middle:* Same but for star-forming galaxies. The best-fitting Schechter functions are over-plotted. The resemblance in the shapes of the separate (quiescent versus star-forming) SMFs is evident. *Right:* Same comparison but for all galaxies, where there clearly is a difference between the cluster and field SMFs. (From [10], with permission)

measurements are particularly difficult to make.

First Science Results

The first results from GOGREEN have already proved surprising. At low redshift, it is well known that clusters host an excess of quiescent (non-star-forming) galaxies relative to the surrounding field. This manifests itself in the stellar mass function (SMF) of quiescent galaxies, which rises steeply toward lower masses in clusters, but drops in the field—a strong indication that normally star-forming galaxies are undergoing a quenching process as they are accreted (e.g., [8]). What we observe at $z > 1$ is strikingly different. The same overall excess of quenched galaxies is observed—the excess is about 40% at both low redshift and $z > 1$. However, unlike at low redshift, the shape of the SMF for these quiescent galaxies is identical to that of the surrounding field, as

shown in Figure 2. The first signs of this were seen in the H -band luminosity function [9], and firmly established with the analysis of the stellar mass functions in [10]. This seems to rule out an accretion-based quenching mechanism that is analogous to what we see locally.

We have also used the spectroscopic features to look in more detail at the star-forming and quiescent galaxy populations. Using the [OII] emission line, we measure the star formation rate (SFR) and its correlation with stellar mass. We find the distribution of these SFRs shows little or no environmental dependence [11]. For the quiescent galaxies, we use the *Prospector* code [12] to simultaneously fit the photometry and spectroscopy and measure the mass-weighted ages of these galaxies. The results, shown in Figure 3, were unexpected and show that these ages are only slightly older

Figure 3. *Left*: Combined posteriors of stellar masses and mass-weighted age (in units of cosmic time), shown as contours. The medians of the individual posteriors are marked with white circles/diamonds (diamonds indicate galaxies that have formed more than 10% of their stars in the last Gyr). *Right*: Combined mass-weighted age posteriors for field and cluster galaxies, shown in three mass bins. The medians (black mark) and 68 percent credible regions (colored bar) of each distribution are marked at the bottom of each subplot. Although there are field galaxies that formed as early as the oldest cluster galaxies, and cluster galaxies that formed as late as the youngest field galaxies, on average field galaxies have more extended SFHs to reach the same final stellar mass. (From [13], with permission)

among the cluster population than in the field [13].

In these papers we consider simple models, whereby the cluster is either a) evolved in a similar way to the field, but with a “head start”, or b) built through the accretion of field galaxies which prematurely end their star formation on some timescale. Neither simple model is able to explain all our observations. It appears that the majority of the cluster population must have ceased forming stars long ago ($z > 4$) and were already quenched when they reached the cluster’s virialized region. Ongoing work includes measuring the halo mass dependence of this effect [14], the abundance of

recently quenched and post-starburst galaxies [15], the morphological differences between cluster and field galaxies [16], the abundance of active galactic nuclei [17] and the cluster dynamical mass profiles [18].

Data Release

The joint GOGREEN and GCLASS data release, described in [4], is distributed via the [CADC](#), and NSF’s [NOIRLab](#). In addition to the reduced images and spectroscopy we provide catalogs of measured and derived quantities (stellar masses, star formation rates, line indices, etc.) and Jupyter notebooks for working with the data.

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